

Impact Of ASUU Strike on Psychosocial Development of Academic Staff in South-East Zone of Nigerian Universities

Okeke, Nkechi Uzochukwu (Ph.D)¹, Anierobi, Elizabeth Ifeoma² & Ezennaka, Anthony Obinna³

^{1&2} Department of Educational Foundations
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

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Abstract

ASUU strike no doubt wheel tremendous influence on the psycho-social development of academic staff in Nigerian universities as a result of the measures often taken by the Government at eruption of strikes ranging from termination of appointment of some ASUU leaders and starvation of employees (non-payment and reduction of salaries). This study investigated the impacts of ASUU strike on the psycho-social development of academic staff in Nigerian universities using ex-post-facto research design. From a population of 12,587 academic staff in 5 Federal Government owned universities in South-East Zone of Nigeria, 1000 subjects were selected for the study using simple random sampling technique. An instrument of 25 items titled "IASPSDAS" was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by specialists in education. Reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha and an alpha coefficient of 0.78 was obtained. Research questions were answered using frequencies and mean. Result revealed that ASUU strike is associated with frustration, withdrawn behaviours, low self-esteem, aggression, deviant behaviours and negative self-concept among others. The researchers recommended that the Federal Government should give education due priority and also honestly (in practical terms) implement all sections on tertiary education as stipulated in her National Policy on Education document among others.

Key words: ASUU, strike and psycho-social development

Introduction

No two individuals are the same even identical twins, therefore, there is bound to be conflict, strife, argument, misunderstanding due to different perceptions, opinions, interpretation and understandings of events and situations. Misunderstanding simply implies a failure to understand correctly, false impression, misapprehension, misconception and misinterpretation. In everyday life events and situations,

misunderstanding seems to be the cause of 90% of all conflicts. Different expectations will always result in conflict.

Okeke and Joe-Akunne (2020) noted that because of mans' imperfection, conflict is inevitable in any human institutions. Conflict simply means a clash between individuals arising out of differences in thought process, attitudes, understanding, interests, requirements and even sometimes perceptions. Conflicts are not found only among individuals but it is common in any human interaction, for example, in homes between couples, in offices between employers and employees, in churches between general overseer and pastors as well as in trade unions between government and members. Supporting the above statement, Kamran, Syed and Yumna (2017) observed that conflicts are indispensable part of any organization as a result of variation in goals of the shareholders, managers and other staff members. They maintained that the root cause of dispute within an organization and among organizational employees is conflict and this opens up an avenue in which employers hinder colleagues from accomplishing their aims and objectives. One of such disputes in organizations especially in higher institutions manifest as strike action.

ASUU rampant strike in Nigeria has roots on unmet needs of lecturers which are essentially psychological. When the needs (physiological, psychological, social, emotional and intellectual) of academic staff of tertiary institutions are not met such conditions as anxiety, stress and frustration sets in. Consequently, behavioural defense mechanisms in form of strikes resulting in indefinite closure of universities are often witnessed, thus, bringing all academic activities to a halt.

ASUU strike appears to hinge heavily on psychological factors impinging on lecturers: Denial of rights/entitlements (ranging from non-payment of salary, promotion arrears and academic earned allowances), stress, pressures, conflicts and frustrations which emanate from such factors like: government's dishonesty, rascal, irresponsibility, violation of agreement, low priority for educational system and insensitivity to other peoples need.

Where the academic staff in tertiary institutions in Nigeria and their employer does not possess conflict resolution skills, great distress can erupt leading to strike. Academic staff in tertiary institutions in Nigeria has a lot of pressure (personal, social and academic) impinging on them. Without adequate conflict resolution skills, they are bound to experience persistent stress and frustrations which constitute the bedrock for ASUU strike. Moreover, measures often taken by the government at the eruption of ASUU strike such as termination of appointment of ASUU leaders, starvation of employees which ranges from withholding of salaries, reduction/slashing often heighten the depth and length of the strike.

Government nonchalant attitude and lack of commitment to the welfare of university education in Nigerian is contrary to the amazing and wonderful goals/objectives of tertiary education stipulated in her National Policy on Education. Close observation of causes of ASUU strikes implicates such factors like erosion of university autonomy and academic freedom, poor remunerative structure and conditions of service, under funding of universities, poor physical conditions of work in the university among others (Wahab, 2018). Government implementation of her policy on university education to the letter is the surest measure for reducing ASUU strikes in Nigeria and until this is done tertiary education in Nigeria remains unproductive, quality education remains a mirage and socioeconomic and cultural welfare of the nation is seriously affected. The conclusion of the matter is that we cannot continue toiling with destinies of the youths who are future leaders of the country therefore government should retrace their steps and give education its rightful place/position in the economy.

Federal Government of Nigeria in her National Policy on Education (2013) emphasized that the goals of tertiary education among others is to:

- contribute to national development through high level manpower training
- provide lifelong learning programmes that prepare students with the knowledge and skills for self reliance and the world of work among others.

They further stated that tertiary education institutions shall pursue these goals through:

- quality teaching and learning, research and development, staff welfare and development programmes among others.

Indeed, this is a wonderful policy on paper but practically unachievable as long as Nigerian government has no interest in the educational sector of the economy. Is it the education that is funded or not funded that will achieve the above stated goals? In a situation where there is constant erosion of university autonomy and academic freedom, poor remunerative structure and conditions of service, under funding of universities, poor physical conditions of work in the universities, delay in the payment of academic staff entitlements, will the above stated objectives be practically achieved? The above questions demands honest and sincere answers and actions if tertiary education should thrive in Nigeria.

One thing is to formulate policy another thing is to implement it to the letter. The National Policy on Education with all its amazing and wonderful goals of tertiary institutions is yet to receive practical steps towards the realization in the country. It is the government failure to practically and effectively implement all the sections of the National Policy on Education concerned with tertiary education that has contributed to ASUU strikes almost on yearly basis from 1999 to 2020.

Literature Review

Brief history of ASUU

ASUU, an acronym for Academic Staff Union of Universities came into existence in 1978 as a successor to the National Association of University Teachers (NAUT). The immediate past national president of ASUU was Professor Abiodun Ogunyemi, a professor of Education at the Olabisi Onabanjo University (OOU) Ago-Iwoye who bowed out after two successful tenures. He was then replaced by a professor of soil science at Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike by name Professor Victor Emmanuel Osodeke on 30th of May, 2021 during a three-day congress of the union which held at Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka in Anambra state of Nigeria.

ASUU is a trade union affiliated to Nigeria Labour Congress (NLC). A trade union is an organized association of workers in a trade, group of trades or profession formed to protect and further their rights and interests. A trade union is a membership-based organization. Most trade unions are independent of any employer. Moreover, trade unions try to develop close working relationships with employers. Pitan and Akindele (2016) noted that trade unions negotiate the terms and conditions of service with the employer, sees to the well-being of members and protects her members from victimizations.

Specifically, ASUU is union of intellectuals from government and state owned universities in Nigeria seeking for the socio-political interest and economic welfare of her members and the country in general. ASUU without doubt is one of the strongest and reliable trade unions in Nigeria and synonymous with strike/struggles because of government insensitivity and irresponsibility. Irresponsibility is the quality of not being trustworthy or dependable, lacking a sense of responsibility, unreliable and untrustworthy. Promise is a debt of the conscience and Nigerian government has time without number proven lack of conscience. Sequel to government's inability to keep to their promise, ASUU almost on yearly basis since 1999 embarked on strike to justify the biblical injunction that the "kingdom of God suffer violence and only the violent will take hold of it". It is quite unfortunate and very shameful that the only language Nigerian government understands is violence and strike. ASUU in the face of all threat of sack and nonpayment of

salaries by her employer has always maintained the biblical Esther stand of “If I die let me die and if I perish let me perish” as the union will never surrender to government intimidation.

Aims and objectives of ASUU

A trade union is an association of workers formed for the purpose of protecting the rights of the workers and improving their economic conditions. Every trade union has the primary goal of securing improvements in working conditions as well as social and political status through collective bargaining. ASUU as a trade union is not an exception. Some authors and researchers including Wahab (2018) and Pitan et al (2016) enumerated some of the general objectives of ASUU to include: Regulation of human relations between academic staff and employers, encouragement of the members to actively participate in affairs of the university such as elections, membership of co-operative societies, university wide conferences, lectures and trainings among others, protection of university autonomy as well as advancement of the social, economic and cultural interest of the nation.

Specifically some of the aims and objectives of ASUU include:

- ASUU gives support to members to ensure the realization of their personal objectives though on the positive side. The biblical injunction that “one can chase a thousand but two people can chase ten thousand” is a reality. This is because an individual while pursuing a goal may feel tired and discouraged, but with the support of a union he will achieve his objectives.
- The academic staff union of universities has the goal of protecting the economic interests of the workers by ensuring improved and reasonable salary package from time to time.
- One of the aims and objectives of ASUU is to protect university autonomy. University autonomy is a somehow difficult concept to define because across nations and overtime, the meaning tends to vary. But in the context of this research work, the researchers explain university autonomy as the power of every university to run and manage its internal affairs without any intervention from external influence. What ASUU does is to protect self governance, self determination, independence or the ability of each university to decide for itself what policies, programmes and actions to adopt towards the fulfillment of her mission and vision.
- Another aims and objectives of ASUU is to assist her members in getting other monetary entitlements from the government such as earned allowance, academic and research grants among others.
- ASUU negotiates between her members and the university management in times of disputes and ensures the settlement.
- ASUU has the goal of assisting indigent students in their educational career. This they achieve by giving orphans, the poor and special students (students with one form of impairment/disability) in the university irrespective of state and tribe/race scholarships to ensure the accomplishment of their academic pursuit.
- The union has the objective of getting certain amenities for the academic staff in addition to higher wages/ improved working conditions.
- As a trade union ASUU provides palliative measures (food items, coping loans and cash assistance) to sick members, the bereaved and also to all desiring members in times of difficulties like strike periods.
- ASUU has the aims and objectives of bringing all academic staff under one umbrella as a family and encourage them to resort to peaceful resolution of conflicts/misunderstanding.
- The union also provides for promotion and training of academic staff and as well assist members to attend higher positions.

Causes of ASUU strike

No right thinking person will expect to get a different result from a situation he/she gives the same approach every time it occurs. As far as the attitude and behaviour of government towards university education in Nigeria remains myopic, insensitive and inhuman, ASUU strike will not cease. It is shocking from literature review that what caused ASUU strike before 2003 are still the cause of ASUU strike today. To buttress the above point, the National Association of University Teachers (1978) stated that previous ASUU strikes were caused by the following: Erosion of university authority, violation of academic freedom, poor conditions of service, poor salary structure, poor/under funding of universities, poor/lack of infrastructural facilities in the universities and delay in the payment of the elongated salary structure.

Wahab (2018) also observed that the Academic Staff in Nigerian universities and the federal government are always in conflict over funding of the Nigerian universities, university autonomy and better/improved working conditions among others. Wahab further posited that each time the two parties come to dialogue in order to settle the disagreement it will end in empty, vain and unfulfilled promise by the government. Still on causes of ASUU strike, Ogbette (2017) noted that students, parents and the society have divided opinions on whom to blame. While one party blame the government for lack of commitment and nonchalant attitude towards education, the other party blame ASUU for their unending demand (Oliver twist), radicalism and confrontational attitude.

Observation of the views of the above authors revealed that nothing has changed. In summary, some of the causes of ASUU strike include among others:

- Government violation of university autonomy which in recent times they want to achieve through the introduction of IPISS.
- Conflicting perceptions, conflicting policies and conflicting goals.
- Misunderstanding (Government sees ASUU as “nuisance” and ASUU view the government as “irresponsible”).
- Unfulfilled promises, unpaid allowances and
- Personality clashes, clash of values among others.

Impact of ASUU strike on psychosocial development of academic staff

ASUU strike no doubt wheel tremendous influence on the psychosocial development of academic staff in universities in Nigeria as a result of measures often taken by the government at the eruption of strikes such as termination of appointment of some ASUU leaders, starvation of employees ranging from nonpayment to reduction/slashing of salaries. In the context of this research work, psychosocial development implies behavioural and social functioning of an individual, that is, the development of a person’s cognitive, emotional, intellectual and social capabilities and functioning over the course of a normal lifespan.

Erikson (1968) a renowned psychologist who is best known for his famous theory of psychosocial development explained psychosocial development as the development of both pro-social behaviour (example cooperation) and anti-social behaviour (example aggression). Erikson noted that psychosocial development involves changes not only in individuals’ overt behaviour but also in their social cognition, the role of biological (nature) and social factors (nurture) in the development of personality. In line with the above, Madariaga, Arribillaga and Zulaika (2014) viewed psychosocial development as peoples capacity to adapt and respond to the demands of the environment thus accomplishing one’s aims and objectives.

The researchers want to point out here that psychologically, social development can be effected by an individuals’ personality, the opportunities they have for social interaction as well as developmental disorders. The impact of starvation, denial of basic rights and entitlements leaves the academic staff in

Nigerian universities in pains, feelings of demoralization and humiliation which often manifest in behaviours like loss of self confidence, low self esteem, negative self concept, frustration, aggression/aggressive behaviours, depression, withdrawn behaviours, loss of friendship, loss of self respect/prestige, shame and reproach, suicidal attempts, hardship in homes/families, misunderstanding in families, threats of divorce, closure of business and deviant behaviours among others. The above mentioned behaviours have serious impact on psychosocial development of an individual as the individual can no longer perform his roles in the family and society ranging from: Provision of daily food, payment of house rent, payment of children school fees, payment of essential bills like electricity, sanitation and water bills, meeting the needs of dependants, relations and loved ones as well as payment of church dues and kindred/town levies.

There is no doubt that the psychosocial development of any person who finds himself/herself in the above mentioned situation is seriously affected.

Research question

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the perceived impacts of ASUU strike on psycho-social development of academic staff in Nigerian universities?
2. What are the possible measures that could be embraced by the government and academic staff to reduce the occurrence of strike in Nigerian universities?

Method

Ex-post-facto research design was used for the study. Nworgu (2015) noted that this type of research design seeks to establish cause-effect relationships. The researcher usually has no control over the variables of interest and therefore, cannot manipulate them. Indeed, the researchers only attempt to link some already existing effects or observations to some variable(s) as causative agent(s). The study was carried out in South-East Zone of Nigeria using all the Federal Government owned universities. The population consists of all 12,587 academic staff (from the cadre of assistant lectures to professors excluding all graduate assistants) in the five (5) universities. Simple random sampling technique was employed to select 1000 academic staff (40 professors, 40 senior lecturers, 40 lecturer 1 cadre, 40 lecturer 2 cadre and 40 assistant lecturers) from each of the five institutions giving a total of 1000 subjects.

A researcher- developed instrument titled “Impact of ASUU Strike on Psycho-Social Development of Academic Staff” (IASPSDAS) was used for data collection. The instrument has two sections with a total of 25 items. It was structured on a modified 4-point Likert scale ranging from strongly agree, agree, disagree to strongly disagree. Three specialists in the Department of Educational Psychology and Measurement and Evaluation from Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka validated the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha with overall reliability coefficient of 0.78.

Four research assistants helped the researchers in distributing the questionnaires to the chosen sample for the study. A total of 1000 copies of the questionnaire given out were successfully completed and returned. Descriptive statistics (frequencies and mean) was used in answering the research questions and acceptance point for the items was 2.50 and any mean below 2.50 was regarded as rejected.

Table 1: Academic Staff Mean Scores on the Impact of Strike on their Psycho-Social Development.

N=1000

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	X	Remark	
1.	Frustration	268	413	19	300	2.65	Agree	
2.	Depression				357	254	204 185 2.70	Agree
3.	Aggression/Aggressive behaviours				367	247	195 191 2.79	Agree
4.	Negative self-concept	313	291	201	195	2.72	Agree	
5.	Low self-esteem				273	309	217 201 2.65	Agree
6.	Lack of self-confidence				231	389	192 188 2.66	Agree
7.	Withdrawn behaviours				279	337	199 185 2.71	Agree
8.	Fatigue				218	378	195 209 2.61	Agree
9.	Loss of friendship				244	362	215 179 2.67	Agree
10.	Loss of self-respect/Prestige				232	378	186 204 2.64	Agree
11.	Shame and reproach				227	348	209 216 2.59	Agree
12.	Suicidal attempts				257	384	177 182 2.72	Agree
13.	Sicknesses and Untimely death				405	235	181 179 2.87	Agree
14.	Hardship in homes				265	207	313 215 2.52	Agree
15.	Misunderstanding in families/threats of divorce.				238	288	212 262 2.50	Agree
16.	Closure of business	235	313	205	217	2.51	Agree	
17.	Deviant behaviours such as illegal sexual acts, sorting for grades/examination scores.				233	297	268 202 2.56	Agree

Table 1 shows that the academic staff with a mean score of 2.50 and above agreed that the 17 items in the instrument which include frustration, depression, negative self-concept, low self-esteem, aggression/aggressive behaviours, withdrawn behaviours, loss of friendship, shame and reproach, suicidal attempts among others were some of the psycho-social impact of ASUU strike on their psycho-social development.

Table 2: Academic Staff Mean Scores on the Possible Measures that could be Effective in Reducing ASUU strike in Nigerian Universities

N=1000

18.	Federal Government should give priority to tertiary education in Nigeria.	223	361	217	199	2.61	Agree
19.	Government honest implementation of all Sections on tertiary education as stipulated in her National Policy on Education document.	261	287	202	250	2.56	Agree
20.	Prompt and complete fulfillment of every reached agreement to the letter.	224	378	207	191	2.64	Agree
21.	Government should refrain from making laws and sanctions violating university autonomy example IPISS.	257	326	215	202	2.64	Agree
22.	Stakeholders in tertiary education (parents, host communities) should come to rescue	250	308	226	216	2.59	Agree

mission in terms of building of halls of residence, classrooms and offices.						
23. Adequate conflict resolution skills should be adopted in place of confrontation every time.	263	246	266	225	2.55	Agree
24. Re-visiting the salary structure of the academic staff.	250	265	242	243	2.52	Agree
25. Empathy for education, good moral conscience and responsibility is vital on the part of Federal Government.	227	374	184	215	2.61	Agree

Table 2 shows the academic staff agreement with a mean score of 2.50 and above that measures such as Federal Government given due priority to tertiary education, Government honesty in implementing all sectors of tertiary education as stipulated in her National Policy on Education document, Government refrain from making laws and sanctions violating university autonomy example IPISS and re-visiting the salary structure of the academic staff among others could be effective measures for reducing the incidence of strike in Nigerian universities.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that ASUU strike has serious impact on the psycho-social developments of academic staff in Nigerian universities. With a mean score of 2.50 and above, the academic staff agreed that some of the impacts of ASUU strike on their psycho-social development include fatigue, frustration, depression, negative self-concept, low self-esteem, withdrawn behaviours, shame and reproach, loss of friendship and deviant behaviours among others. ASUU strike with all its attendant humiliating and derogatory situation exposes the individual to fatigue. This agrees with the findings of Nurelina (2021) that often fatigue takes time to unfold that is, it is progressive in nature. It starts gradually with little symptoms and if not handled immediately may result to lasting and sound sense of panic for work.

ASUU strike from the findings of this study affects academic staff self esteem which has to do with a positive or negative orientation toward oneself an overall evaluation of one's worth or value. Self esteem can simply be explained as how much you appreciate and like yourself regardless of the circumstances. An individual's self esteem is defined by many factors including self confidence, feeling of security, identity, sense of belonging and feeling of competence. The findings of this study aligns with Kendra (2021) observation that people are motivated to have high self esteem and having it indicates positive self regard not egotism and also influence a person's mental well being and overall quality in life. When an individual stays for months without going to work, earning no salary, unable to perform his/her primary roles as a father/mother in the home his/her worth is affected and thus low self esteem. In this situation, the individual in question is less sure of their abilities and may doubt his/her decision making process. He/she is uncertain of reaching certain goals. They have problems/challenges with relationships and expressing their needs. They may also experience low levels of confidence and feel unlovable and unworthy.

Negative self concept is one of the psychological impacts of ASUU strike on academic staff of universities as revealed from the findings of this study. Self concept is the perception that we have of ourselves. Simply put, self concept is the answer to questions like "Who am I?" It is knowledge about one's own tendencies, thoughts, preferences and habits, hobbies, skills and areas of weakness. The awareness of who we are is our concept of our self. An individual's worth is not assessed in words but in "Power and Action". Therefore an individual's inability to perform his primary roles in the home and society reduces his worth

and self-confidence. In Igbo traditional society in Nigeria where the researchers come from, people's worth generally are assessed and respected on the basis of "monetary worth" and not on "certificate held and spoken grammars". Burton (2015) cited in Courtney Acknerman (2021) agrees with the findings of this study that self confidence is about your trust in yourself and your ability to deal with challenges, solve problems and engage successfully with the world and is measured more on external effects such as value and success than on internal effects. A situation where a person cannot solve immediate problems and needs due to non-payment of monthly salary his/her self confidence will be affected.

Denial of salaries, unending poverty and lack which accompany ASUU strike in universities in Nigeria are difficult experiences for a person to endure. The findings of this study revealed that this could lead to depression which is a common and serious medical ill health that negatively affects how you feel; the way you think and how you act. Supporting the findings of this study, American Psychiatric Association (2013) noted that depression causes feelings of sadness and/or loss of interest in activities you once enjoyed. It can lead to a variety of emotional and physical problems and can decrease your ability to function at work and at home with such symptoms as feeling sad, loss of interest in earlier enjoyed activities, inability to sleep, feeling of guilt and worthless, difficulty in concentration and thought of death or suicide.

Furthermore, Akinloye and Uhunnwuaugho (2018) supporting the findings of this study assert that the effect of a frustrating occurrence such as ASUU strike may lead to many emotional and affective responses such as acute stress, lasting anger, sadness and rage. They observed that those elements often mixed together in a variety of proportion constitute frustration. Psychologically, if an individual continues pursuing a goal without any result, frustration will set in. This can lead to other emotions that affect his or her well being and mental health such as loss of confidence, stress, anger, aggressive behaviour, irritability and depression.

ASUU strike and its effect has brought untold hardship on many lecturers, their families and loved ones. As an adult, one might act aggressively in response to negative experiences such as hunger, debt, poverty and lack among others. Aggression occurs when a person is angry, in a bad mood, tired, in pains or frustrated. One is more likely to be aggressive when he/she is experiencing negative emotions. Idleness and frustration during ASUU strikes can lead to indulgence in deviant behaviours like staying away from the home late in the night, illegal business, extra-marital relationship, alcohol and drug among others. Individuals without strong will-power often engage in these behaviours as defense mechanisms to obtaining short time happiness and escape from the confrontational spouse at home. Also, many lecturers have lost their lives as a result of ASUU strike and the accompanying difficulties. Some individuals who had one form of terminal sickness or the other died as a result of lack of medical check-up and treatment while some died in the process of running about to see both ends meet in their homes. Some turned their private cars to commercial taxi and in the process lost their lives in road accident.

Finally, the findings of this study revealed through the academic staff mean responses of 2.50 and above that measures such as Government given education due priority, Government honest implementation in practical terms all the sections on tertiary education as stipulated in her National Policy on Education document, increase of the salary structure of academic staff in Nigerian universities and Government refrain from making policies violating the university autonomy example IPISS could be effective in reducing the occurrence of strike in Nigerian universities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers recommend as follows:

1. All sections of the National Policy on Education (2013) concerned with tertiary education in Nigeria should be practically and effectively implemented without further delay.

2. Federal and state government should give the education sector its rightful place in Nigerian economy. Education is the root of every other sector in the economy ranging from medical, industrial, political and social and therefore should receive the highest budget allocation. University education should be properly and adequately funded to achieve the desired objectives, produce self-reliant graduates thus reducing unemployment and social vices in the country and as well boost the socioeconomic development of the country.
3. Government should abide with any reached agreement with ASUU. The government refusal to fulfill the agreement reached with ASUU since 1999 has however been the basic reason the union goes on strike almost every year (from 1999 till last year 2020). This is quite unfortunate. Good human relationship demands that agreement be kept and in case of any reason for otherwise both parties should be aware on time and not after the time frame.
4. One thing that has threatened university education in Nigeria is constant ASUU strike which is triggered by government dishonesty and lack of empathy for education. The researchers recommend that government should retrace their steps by avoiding erosion of university autonomy and academic freedom, improve the working conditions of academic staff and improve on physical conditions of work in the university in terms of infrastructures (classroom, libraries, multi-purpose halls, laboratories, halls of residence and offices) and teaching and learning materials.

Conclusion

This study concluded that ASUU strike no doubt wheel tremendous influence on the psycho-social development of academic staff in Nigerian Universities as a result of measures often taken by the Federal government at eruption of strikes ranging from termination of appointment of some ASUU leaders to starvation of employees (which manifest in non-payment to reduction/slashing of salaries). The study further revealed that such measures like: Government given education in Nigeria due priority, Government honest and practical implementation to the letter all sections on tertiary education as stipulated in her National Policy on Education document, improving the salary structure of academic staff in Nigerian universities among others.

References

- Akinloye, E.O. & Uhunnwuaugho, S.O. (2018). Analysis of the effects of frequent strikes on academic performance of students in universities in Nigeria: Edo state as a focal point. *African research review (International multi-disciplinary journal, Bahr Dar Ethiopia)*. 12 (1), 56-65. Online-DOI: <http://dx.doi-org/10.4314/afrev.v/2i/7>
- American Psychiatric Association (2013). What is depression? Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders. Retrieved from <https://www.psychiatry.org>> Courtney Acknerman, M.A. (2021). What is self esteem? A psychologist explains. Retrieved from <https://positivepsychology.com>sel...>
- Erikson, E.H. (1968). Identity: Youth crisis (2nd edition). New York: Norton.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). National Policy on Education. Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Kamran, K., Syed, K. & Humna, I. (2017). Causes, effects and remedies in conflict management. *South East Asian journal of management, 10*(2). Online- DOI: 10.21002/seam.VIOi2.7733. Retrieved from researchgate.
- Kendra, C. (2021). What is self esteem? Retrieved from <https://www.verywellmind.com>>
- Madariaga, J.M., Arribillaga, A. & Zulaika, L.M. (2014). Components and relationships of a structural model of psychosocial adjustment in adolescence. *International journal on developmental educational psychology*. (6), 303-310. Retrieved from googlescholar.
- National Association of University Teachers (NAUT, 1978). Reports presented at the Emergency meeting of the council of university teachers. NAUT News-letter, 2(1).
- Nurelina, A. (2021). What is withdrawal behaviour? Retrieved from <https://www.scribd.com>>document

- Nworgu, B.G. (2015). *Education Research: Basic Issues and Methodology* (3rd edition). University Trust Publishers: Nsukka-Nigeria
- Ogbette, A.S. (2017). Causes, effects and management of ASUU strikes in Nigeria, 2003-2013. *Journal of research and development (JRND)*. 3 (3). Retrieved from researchgate.
- Okeke, N.U. & Joe-Akunne, C.O. (2020). Psychological dimensions of violence and influence on emotional adjustment of adolescents in tertiary institutions in Anambra state. *Journal of the Nigerian academy on education*. 16 (1), 238-250.
- Pitan, O.O. & Akindele, S.T. (2016). University management perception of academic staff union of universities (ASUU) struggles in Nigeria: Implications for counseling and productivity. *International journal of humanities and social science*, 5(2), 33-37
- Wahab, B. (2018). All the times ASUU has gone on strike since 1999. Retrieved from <https://www.pulse.ng>